

Mathematics in Civil Engineering Research and Practice

Alexios E. Tamparopoulos

University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU), Vienna, Austria

Abstract

Mathematics is in continuous interaction with the natural sciences and human activity. The use of computers today has transformed this relationship and has consequently shifted the already subtle boundary between pure and applied mathematics. The present article attempts to identify the nature and scope of the mathematical tools that dominate research and practice of civil engineering, as well as the reasons why the relationship between mathematics and application has now undergone a profound change.

1 Introduction

Mathematics is in continuous interaction with human activity. On the one hand, mathematical discoveries provide the applied sciences with a constantly expanding range of theoretical tools, which often acquire unexpected utility (Wigner, 1960). On the other hand, the demands of practical applications, in turn, feed back into pure mathematics with new impulses and paradigms. Thus, mathematics and the natural sciences evolve in tandem, maintaining a rather complementary relationship.

Since the mid-20th century, this relationship appears to have undergone a decisive change. The widespread use of the computer has enabled and facilitated the analysis of physical problems that do not admit closed-form mathematical solutions—which is, in fact, the most common case. Moreover, human activity is becoming increasingly complex relative to the available mathematical models, as it seeks to realise applications that require high accuracy, reliable estimation, comprehensive documentation, and demanding prediction. These new needs and capabilities, along with other specific factors related to the contemporary social and economic organisation of the Western world, have dramatically altered the scope and intensity of the interaction between practice and theoretical mathematics.

The present article, starting from a brief historical overview of the mathematical foundations of engineering, seeks to identify the nature and scope of the mathematical tools that currently dominate research and practice in civil engineering, drawing on recent scientific publications and presentations at international engineering conferences. It further examines the reasons why the interaction between theory and practice has changed. At the same time, based on these findings, it attempts to shed light on the boundary between pure and applied mathematics—if such a boundary ultimately exists.

2 The Classical Period of Engineering

The classical period of engineering, that is, the period prior to the information revolution, can be divided into two main subperiods, with the emergence of calculus as a milestone. On this basis, what follows is a brief overview of the engineer's relationship with theoretical mathematics.

English translation of the original Greek paper presented at the 5th International week dedicated to Maths, 27–31 March 2013, Thessaloniki, Greece. Original Greek version available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20023525>

2.1 Before the 18th Century: Engineering as Geometry

Engineering, from Antiquity until the 18th century, was inextricably intertwined with plane and solid geometry. The engineer was essentially a geometer, who also possessed empirical knowledge of materials and their properties. Thus, distinguished engineers typically also left their mark on theoretical geometry. Typical historical examples include figures such as Archimedes of Syracuse, Heron of Alexandria, Leonardo da Vinci, and Jakob Steiner. Da Vinci, in particular, often depicted mechanical and geometric objects simultaneously in his drawings (Moon, 2007), considering it natural for material and ideal forms to coexist at the same stage of the study of the work.

The absence of advanced materials, techniques, and scientific tools did not prevent engineers of Antiquity from designing and executing works that still inspire admiration today. The famous *Tunnel of Eupalinos*, excavated in the 6th century BC on the island of Samos under the direction of Eupalinos of Megara, had a length slightly exceeding 1000 m (Angelakis & Koutsoyiannis, 2003) and, as reported by Herodotus in his *Histories*, was constructed from both ends simultaneously, that is, with excavation proceeding from two faces. Such an undertaking required advanced geodetic knowledge and numerical precision; Eupalinos is said to have been the first to employ orthogonal coordinates (Bantelas et al., 1999). More generally, it is certain that such works could not have been realised with the formally available knowledge of the time, but required what we would now call "Research & Development".

However, exclusive reliance on models of theoretical geometry, combined with the mere accumulation of empirical knowledge about the physical world, could not lead to sustained progress in engineering science. At least three elements were still lacking: (1) the physical laws governing material behaviour, (2) the incorporation of uncertainty, and (3) the capacity to perform large volumes of numerical calculations in a short time. The first of these developed rapidly in the 18th and 19th centuries, primarily through calculus, following the broader flourishing of physics. The latter two had to await the 20th century and the information age.

2.2 After the 18th Century: Engineering as Applied Analysis

The discovery of calculus in the late 17th century, chiefly by Newton and Leibniz, opened new horizons for all the natural sciences and decisively transformed the relationship between engineering and mathematics. Thereafter, data derived from experiment or observation no longer led merely to empirical information, but to differential equations. These equations, in turn, yielded either closed-form analytical solutions or approximate numerical ones for a vast range of problems. The world was no longer merely a representation of dimensions, and the physical laws governing the behaviour and failure of materials had gradually begun to be revealed.

A characteristic example is the Euler–Bernoulli equation, which describes the bending deformation w of an elastic beam under a load q (Kassimali, 2011):

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} \left(EI \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right) = q \quad (1)$$

where x is the spatial coordinate, E is the modulus of elasticity of the material, and I is the second moment of inertia of the cross-section. Despite its simplicity, this equation provides analytical solutions for most applications involving transverse loading of beam type elements, used in conventional structures in engineering practice today.

Similarly, one may refer to the well-known Navier–Stokes equations (White, 2002), which describe the motion of fluids and have played a decisive role in the development of hydraulics. Complex analysis was applied to the study of groundwater flow, while the differential geometry of surfaces was applied to the analysis of loaded plates. The research engineer, at this stage in the history of science, is no longer merely a geometer, but also a profound practitioner of mathematical analysis. In essence, the foundations of the subjects that form the core of undergraduate engineering education were laid during this period.

At the same time, during this period, engineering applications provided theoretical mathematics with a wealth of stimuli, which can still be traced today, in part, in the terminology in use. Thus, we

speak of inflection points and stationary points of a function, flux and curl of a vector field, conservative and incompressible fields (Georganopoulos, 1991), terms that bear witness to the physical origin of the corresponding concepts.

3 Mathematics and Contemporary Research

As noted earlier, engineering moved from the study of space (geometry) to that of variations (calculus), but two fundamental elements were still lacking: the incorporation of uncertainty and the ability to perform large volumes of numerical computations in a short time. This situation began to change rapidly in the second half of the 20th century.

3.1 The Recognition of Uncertainty

With regard to the first of these missing elements, namely the incorporation of uncertainty, engineering provided fertile ground for the development of statistics and probability theory. The physical and mechanical properties of materials, as well as the loads induced on structures by natural actions, are no longer treated as fully known, nor are they determined in a strictly deterministic way. Uncertainty, whether aleatory (inherent variability) or epistemic (lack of knowledge), plays a significant role in mathematical models (Der Kiureghian, 2009). In addition, significant progress has been made through the development of alternative methods for optimisation and decision-making under uncertainty: stochastic processes, fuzzy sets, neural networks, interval analysis, genetic algorithms, Dempster–Shafer theory, gray numbers, and others.

These methods, however exotic or elaborate they may have appeared a decade ago, now frequently appear in engineering research publications. Indicative examples include the use of Bayesian inference (Papadioti & Papadimitriou, 2013) and genetic algorithms (Wang & Huang, 2013) for structural damage identification, gamma processes in modelling bridge deterioration (Strauss et al., 2013), neural networks in problems related to petroleum extraction (Baraldi et al., 2012), clustering techniques for the control of nuclear reactors (Mandelli et al., 2012), and integral geometry in the study of heterogeneity in structural materials (Stroeve & Hu, 2006), among others. Most of these methods, however, require computational power far exceeding human capabilities. Thus, the development of these techniques has proceeded in parallel with the advent of modern computing.

3.2 The Use of Computing

Around the middle of the 20th century, computers made their appearance, radically transforming almost every form of human activity. Initially, they were extremely expensive, bulky and difficult to operate, available only to a small number of research groups, but they gradually became indispensable tools for every engineer. Ultimately, the research engineer has today become a highly capable computer user: spreadsheets, structural analysis software, statistical packages, programming languages, and CAD systems are considered indispensable tools.

However, the computer did not merely serve as a means of reducing computational time; by removing the time constraints on numerical calculations, it also provided an impetus for the development of new mathematical techniques. It is worth noting that immediately following the appearance of the first operational electronic computer, the ENIAC in 1946, the Monte Carlo method (Metropolis & Ulam, 1949) was developed, which today constitutes a cornerstone of applied mathematics and stochastic analysis. In particular, the method is commonly applied in structural reliability analysis.

Of course, however useful the computer may be, it cannot produce mathematics. It does, however, enable the use of mathematical tools—often in simplified forms—freed from the restrictive rigour of their theoretical origins. This has significantly expanded the engineer’s scope of practice, while at the same time diminishing intuitive capacity. Blind trust in computer-generated results often leads to insufficient verification of input data (the “garbage in–gospel out” syndrome). At the same time, the task of the researcher increasingly consists in selecting the appropriate method, collecting the data, and formulating

the problem as input to an automated process, while remaining largely a spectator to its underlying scientific substance. Ultimately, the research engineer employs increasingly sophisticated mathematical techniques, which they understand less and less.

3.3 The Role of Mathematical Tools in Contemporary Engineering

The focus of civil engineering no longer appears to lie in the natural sciences, but rather in the design sciences, where attention has shifted from the study of natural phenomena to the technical service of the individual and society (March & Smith, 1995). This development has been driven by the complex structure of Western social and economic organisation; for example, a major infrastructure project must today be analysed in depth with respect to its environmental impact, human safety, public utility, legal risks, economic viability, and a range of other factors. Within this vortex of diverse requirements, mathematical rigour often recedes into the background.

Furthermore, the contemporary trend toward interdisciplinary collaboration, facilitated by modern communication technologies and necessitated by the vast expansion of scientific knowledge, has relieved the engineer of the obligation to verify every step of their theoretical reasoning. Research teams often include a mathematician or a statistician, tasked with the selection and utilisation of theoretical mathematical tools. Thus, one can find engineering applications grounded in complex mathematical theories.

As noted earlier, mathematical rigour is often relaxed in favour of results. A characteristic example illustrating the lack of mathematical strictness, and the corresponding flexibility this affords in engineering research, is the concept of probability. Thus, in practical engineering applications, one encounters at least four distinct interpretations (Teigen et al., 1999; Goodwin & Wright, 2004; Oberguggenberger & Fellin, 2005):

1. The classical interpretation, in which probabilities are assigned to events through combinatorial analysis.
2. The frequentist interpretation, in which probabilities are defined as relative frequencies of outcomes in controlled experiments.
3. The possibilistic/subjective interpretation, in which probabilities represent degrees of belief, assigned subjectively to events.
4. The propensity interpretation, in which probabilities are interpreted as physical propensities arising from underlying causal mechanisms.

Perhaps the most significant difference between theoretical and applied mathematics appears to be of an aesthetic nature. In theoretical mathematics, beauty resides within, in the scientific development itself (Colyvan, 2001), whereas in applied mathematics it lies externally, in the influence that this development exerts on the human environment. As the engineer's control over the objects of study is strengthened and expanded, the (already subtle) boundary between theoretical and applied mathematics shifts in favour of purpose itself, namely, practical application.

4 Summary

The complex social and economic structure of the Western world, the increased technical and functional demands of engineering structures, the unprecedented growth of scientific knowledge, as well as other factors related to contemporary socio-economic organisation, have disrupted the relationship between theoretical and applied mathematics. It appears that a decisive role is played by the advent and widespread penetration of computers into every phase of human activity. Gradually, the mathematical tools in the hands of the research engineer appear increasingly to be becoming automated, while mathematical rigour recedes in favour of efficiency. At the same time, the range of available mathematical methods that find direct application in civil engineering research and practice has expanded remarkably.

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